

THEORETICAL ISSUES OF RESEARCH METHODS IN ABU RAYHAN BERUNI AND HISTORY

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Abstract. *The article deals with modern history science and concrete (concrete) society as its subject and its decline since its formation, studying history in Beruni's works, Beruni's historical comparative methods.*

Key words: *Abu Rayhan Beruni, work "India", research, Economical.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ МЕТОДОВ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В АБУ РАЙХАН БЕРУНИ И ИСТОРИИ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается современная историческая наука и конкретное (конкретное) общество как ее предмет и его упадок с момента его становления, изучение истории в трудах Беруни, историко-сравнительные методы Беруни.*

Ключевые слова: *Абу Райхан Беруни, работа «Индия», исследования, Экономика.*

History and the science of history is a complex of social sciences, which studies the processes and events in the economic, political, social and cultural life of mankind throughout the past in a concrete way and with the help of various methods, divided into periods and generally. Economic history, political history, cultural history, military history, diplomatic history, and historical geography are branches of history. The components of the science of history are special historical sciences and archeology and ethnology, and the history of science and culture, the history of art are studied in connection with these areas.

Modern science of history is a complex of knowledge made up of separate departments and fields, and its research issues are very complicated due to the complexity of methods and the breadth of scope. Today, as a modern history science and its subject, concrete (concrete) society and its development in time and space from its formation to its decline are understood as a whole and at the same time its internal structural structures, as well as its connection and relations with other concrete (concrete) societies. In this regard, the opinions of Abu Rayhan Beruni are also noteworthy, he stated that "... the earliest and most famous of the ancient histories is the beginning of humanity", that is, Beruni said that the beginning of history is related to the formation of human society. shows. It is worth noting that in Beruni's works there are references to the study of history and the correct use of sources in this process, and especially that most of them correspond to the views expressed by various authors in the methodology of modern history.

In modern history textbooks, one can see a number of opinions about Beruni's practical work in historical research. For example, "A great scientist of the Middle Ages, Abu Rayhan Beruni, made a great contribution to the development of the principles of scientific knowledge and understanding. Beruni used the historical comparative method very widely. In the process of writing the work "India", he wrote that "I present the laws of the Indians as they are, and at the same time, using the example of the Greeks, I determine their similarities and closeness"¹. A number of opinions have been expressed regarding history and the science of history, one of which

elaborates the meaning of the other. It is noted in the literature that the word history refers to the reality, life, evidence and events related to the past that arose in the process of social development. - is used in the sense of a specific time, date, indicating when the event took place. "Each of the peoples spread over all countries has a separate history, it considers [the beginning of its history - Z.I.] from its kings, prophets, states, or from one of the events I mentioned above.

With the help of this history, it determines the necessary [terms] in dealings and knowing the times, and this history distinguishes them from other peoples" in which Beruni states that each nation has a separate history and this history distinguishes them from others, but at the same time, it is precisely these distinguishing differences or differences. the fact that he wanted to analyze how it is interpreted in those nations through comparison, by using the synchronic method in the methodology of modern history and the methods of historical comparison at the same time, to his goal, that is, the scientificity of the book he is writing can be seen to have tried to provide. The analysis of the method of historical comparison, which is of great importance in modern history studies, in the scientific work of Abu Rayhan Beruni, and at the same time, it is evidence that the scientific importance of such theoretical views put forward by scholars was high even in the 10th century. The interpretation of "history" is particularly important in history, historical sources and works, especially in Eastern historiography.

According to another source explaining this science, history is a science that studies any development process in nature and society, and in another interpretation, the development of humanity and civilizations that are its products, the development of society and states in the past. The science of history studies the events and processes (development of society) that have occurred in the life of society throughout the entire past of humanity¹. It can be observed that the terms history and history are used in different contexts in historical sources and classical literature. Tarikh (in Arabic - happened, happened) is a sign, poetic style or a word with a hidden meaning. History is often written in poetic language in connection with the death of one or another famous person, to signify or refer to the date of a historical event. When the words and phrases used in history are added together with the numbers of the Arabic letters that make them up, the numbers that represent a certain date come out¹.

History is one of the main features of Eastern historiography, and "histories" have also been found to have important source characteristics. According to the content of the dates, it represents the information in the sources. In the theoretical approaches of the science of modern history, it is emphasized that the information is expressed openly and in a hidden state (the latter is more common)², while the information given in the histories of Eastern historiography is more often found in a hidden state. Therefore, it is important for a historian or researcher to know the Arabic alphabet and especially the abjad in order to identify and extract this information from the text. It can be observed in the examples of Eastern historiography that the date envisaged by the author during the writing of historical works is expressed in the form of words or problems and interpreted in the style of history.

Accordingly, history is divided into two types: Sarih (open, clear) and Tamiya (hidden, hidden). If the date is clearly expressed in the yellow type of history, then the substance of the history is found first in the tamiya. There are many cases where dates are used in historical works and sources. From both of the above cases, it can be seen that in Eastern historiography and in the fields of modern historical science methodology, the presence of information in a clear and open

state, as well as in a hidden state (within the meaning of the word) during the interpretation of the information in the sources and the text, is of particular importance. is being highlighted. "One of the writers asked me about the histories of [different] peoples, their beginnings and branches, that is, about the differences of the historians and the reasons for these differences...." If we pay attention to the words of Beruni, it can be seen that the main thing that is being asked are the histories and the circumstances related to them. In the comment section of the translation of Beruni's work "India", the phrase "histories" is interpreted as follows, that is, "here the word history is used in the sense of a year, an era." In our opinion, it would be appropriate to give it in the form of "history" and not "history" in this place, and this word does not mean the meaning of the year or the era, but the date of the historical event.

It would be appropriate to emphasize that 'z. This opinion is confirmed by Beruni's other words, that is, in the question of the connection of historical processes with time and space, Beruni quotes the following words: the term is called history. In that year, by various signs and evidence [some] ... something important must have happened, which would not appear without long centuries and many times (proof of the concept that history takes place in space and time - Z.I.). Through such events, certain times and dates are determined (here, the phrase "events" can be understood and accepted as evidence that identifies or proves historical processes - Z.I.)..."

In this, Beruni can achieve a clear result by comparing the available information or evidence, that is, by using the method of historical comparison, in which the main issue is the variety of information found in different sources and their different aspects, reducing the conflict as much as possible and putting it before the research. it shows whether it is the most reliable information directed at a specific target or whether evidence should be extracted. It can be seen from these words that one of the most basic methods of modern history research - historical comparison method - was shown by Abu Rayhan Beruni in the 10th century and remained in historical research and historiography for the next ten centuries.

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